

THE DEVELOPMENT OF RESEARCH SKILLS AMONG PROSPECTIVE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

Kh.M. Karomatovna¹, S.U. Shaydullaeva²

PhD, Associate Professor, Department of Primary Education Pedagogy, Faculty of Primary Education, Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami¹

Basic doctoral student of Tashkent State Pedagogical University²

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Abstract. *Students' research activities are primarily considered a means of enhancing the quality of education and professional training. This article examines the development of research skills among prospective primary school teachers as a social necessity. The pedagogical aspects of the social factors influencing the development of research competencies are analyzed in relation to their role in the professional growth of future primary school teachers.*

Keywords: *prospective primary school teacher, research activity, academic work, interest, motivation and encouragement, professional training.*

Introduction. Research conducted within higher education institutions indicates that students are generally unaware of academic conferences, competitions, and research contests. This is particularly evident during the first two years of study, where approximately three-quarters of students' report having no knowledge of such opportunities.

Furthermore, in response to the question, "What kind of research activities do you engage in?", two-thirds of the students answered "none." The remaining third referred to "theoretical inquiries," which, in many cases, simply involved reading additional literature in preparation for seminars.

Thus, the majority of students do not participate in research activities, and if we apply a stricter interpretation of the concept of "science" based on their responses, this proportion becomes even smaller. The clear conclusion is that, across various types and profiles of higher education institutions surveyed, insufficient attention is being paid to engaging students in scientific research.

Thus, an important means of improving the quality of professional training for future specialists is not being sufficiently utilized. This leads us to consider the issue of methods for fostering students' engagement in scientific research.

First and foremost, it is essential to pay attention to the challenges as well as the motivating factors and incentives that can be relied upon. This issue has two significant aspects. On the one hand, much depends on the specific characteristics of how educational and research activities are organized at a given institution—not only for students but in general. On the other hand, the overall societal prestige of science and the degree of attention it receives "from the top down" can play a major role. We will begin by addressing the latter.

Among other questions, students were asked: "In your opinion, is science a prestigious field of activity in our society?" The responses were, arguably, rather optimistic. In particular, only 3.5% of students stated that science is "not prestigious at all," while the majority expressed the opposite view. Some even claimed that scientific activity holds more prestige than any other field. This suggests that respect for science and scientists still exists among today's youth.

However, at the same time, one-quarter of students noted that the prestige of science has declined in recent years, while slightly less than one-third found it difficult to answer the question. It is also worth noting that the most skeptical attitudes were observed among third-year students—precisely the stage at which students are more likely to become actively involved in research.

The next two questions, which require more precise analysis, delve deeper into this topic. The first was formulated as follows: “Do you wish to engage in scientific activity after graduation?” Less than half of the respondents expressed such a desire (with lower numbers among underclassmen and slightly higher among senior students). Others indicated that while they were not opposed to scientific activity, some were more interested in guaranteed financial stability, while others expressed doubts about their own capabilities. The remaining students provided vague or negative responses.

Methodology. The information presented above indicates the presence of significant social and economic factors that limit both the interest of prospective primary school teachers in science and their participation in research activities. Therefore, if we aim to utilize research as a means of improving the quality of professional training for students today, it is essential to rely on the overall prestige of science in society. Additionally, it would be reasonable to make use of the opportunities that may be available—albeit to varying degrees—at certain educational institutions.

In this context, it is worth emphasizing that the general socio-psychological environment is quite favorable. The majority of respondents noted that engagement in research activities (or research in general) is widely supported by students themselves, university professors, and even their parents.

The role of educators in introducing students to scientific research is crucial. Prospective primary school teachers tend to seek internal, subjective motivation. However, when evaluating themselves, they often emphasize external incentives rather than intrinsic motivation.

To develop students’ engagement in scientific research within higher education institutions, the following key measures were identified based on the findings:

- Improvement of the university’s material and financial resources, technical support (including access to computers), and provision of scientific literature;
- Enhancement and reform of educational formats, with greater emphasis on practical training;
- Strengthening of the focus on employability within educational processes;
- Implementation of student incentive mechanisms (e.g., material rewards, exemption from assignments or exams);
- Better organization of scientific research activities within universities and more effective involvement of students in such activities;
- Promotion of research activities among students;
- Cultivation and development of students’ interest in scientific research.

Most respondents are indeed aware of and capable of assessing the situation in their universities and institutions. The implementation of these suggestions—or at least some of them—could meaningfully contribute to the development of student research activity, thereby enhancing the overall quality of professional training for future specialists.

From a systems approach perspective, the encouragement of students' research activity represents an interactive system involving the object (the student), the subject of stimulation (educators and academic staff), and the environmental conditions. Through this interaction, students' needs and motivations for participating in various forms of research are developed and enriched.

The model for developing research skills through the organization of student research activities is illustrated in Figure 1. This model encompasses the content, components, forms, and tools for developing the research competencies of prospective primary school teachers, as well as the criteria and indicators for assessing the level of skill development.

In our study, the primary goal is to develop research competencies among university students by encouraging their engagement in scientific activities. A crucial component of the system that promotes student research activity is the integration of goals, principles, content, organizational forms, methods, and tools of educators and academic disciplines, which collectively ensure student involvement in research processes.

These stimulating agents (educators and academic actors) form a system of methods and tools that create opportunities to foster and reinforce students' interest and participation in research, as well as their need to engage in inquiry and experimentation. Again, in our research, the development of students' research skills through the stimulation of research activity within higher education institutions is considered the central objective.

The essential component of this system lies in the unified efforts of educators and academic disciplines, whose aims, principles, and methods are aligned to ensure active student involvement in research activities. This system supports the development and consolidation of students' motivation and interest in research through structured engagement in inquiry-based practices.

The objective, as a core component of the system under study, ensures the integrity and coherence of the entire process. The primary goal of educators' activity is to stimulate students' scientific engagement as a key factor in their professional development. In a broader sense, the aim of organizing and promoting research activities among prospective primary school teachers is twofold: to enhance the scientific preparedness of professionally educated specialists and to identify talented young individuals.

To successfully achieve this objective, several key tasks must be addressed, including:

- Diagnosing students' research potential and readiness to engage in scientific inquiry;
- Teaching students the fundamentals of research;
- Preparing students for creative scientific work and ensuring an organic integration of this preparation within their overall training;
- Creating conditions for the identification and development of students' individual creative abilities;
- Selecting talented youth who demonstrate a capacity and desire for scientific and pedagogical activity;
- Preparing specialists who possess design thinking skills, are capable of developing well-founded scientific and practical solutions for production settings, and who have developed self-management competencies;
- Ensuring the integration of academic coursework with students' scientific research activities;

- Supporting the implementation and dissemination of students' research findings.

The next component of the model is the organizational and activity-based component. This element of the model defines the structure and organization of pedagogical activity necessary for achieving the stated objectives and completing the identified tasks. Within the context of prospective primary school teachers, the following elements are substantiated as core components of research:

№	Бўлажак бошланғич синф ўқитувчиларнинг тадқиқотчилик кўникмаларининг компонентлари	Мазмуни
1	Мотивацион компонент	Бўлажак бошланғич таълим ўқитувчиларинг тадқиқотчилик кўникмасининг аҳамиятини англаш ва тадқиқотчилик кўникмасини ўзлаштиришга эҳтиёжнинг мавжудлиги;
2	Когнитив компонент	Тадқиқотчилик фаолияти соҳасидаги билимларнинг эгалланганлиги;
3	Технологик компонент	Тадқиқотчилик характеридаги ўқув-касбий топшириқларни бажаришда асосий тадқиқотчилик кўникмаларининг намоён бўлиши.

As is well known, the fundamental law of the pedagogical process is to ensure the transmission of the social experience of older generations to the younger ones. This is closely connected with specific laws that manifest as regularities. Since the encouragement of students' research activity constitutes a substantial aspect of the teacher's educational function, it is, first and foremost, subject to the general laws, principles, and rules of education—extensively studied, justified, and described in educational literature and grounded in scientific theory.

Results and discussion. It is worth noting that scholars and practitioners have identified numerous didactic patterns. For instance, I.P. Podlasy's textbook alone presents over 70 different types of research-related aspects within the learning process. This significantly facilitates the task of justifying models that promote students' research activities.

We consider regularities to be stable systems of objectively existing relationships and interactions among phenomena or their individual components. According to a number of foreign researchers, one of the key aims of education is to develop students' ability to identify, formulate, and solve scientifically relevant problems that have practical significance.

Within the educational process, students must acquire skills for organizing and independently conducting research, discovering facts, comparing them, establishing relationships between them, generalizing, and drawing conclusions. To do so, they must be able to utilize knowledge obtained from various sources, interpret this information, correctly format research results, and be able to defend their findings.

Participation in research activities contributes to a student's intellectual, professional, and personal development. From this standpoint, it is reasonable to refer to the approaches of international scholars when interpreting the concepts used here—such as "research," "scientific research," and "research activity."

Abroad, these concepts are interpreted differently by scholars. In a broad sense, scientific research is understood as an original discovery that generates new knowledge. However, it should also be noted that the term "research" implies rediscovering already known knowledge from a new perspective.

In foreign literature, scientific research is often defined as the systematic, controlled, empirical, and critical investigation of hypothetical assumptions regarding observable phenomena in nature. It is seen as an intellectually guided scientific inquiry aimed at discovering and systematizing new knowledge, as well as developing and enhancing existing knowledge and practice.

The promotion of students' research activity is determined by the objective needs and interests of society. In terms of production, this refers to preparing qualified professionals, and in terms of science, it serves as the foundational and most general model. The social conditioning of this process is reflected in its goals, tasks, content, means of encouraging students' research activity, and the conditions that determine its effectiveness.

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